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STATUS OF RETAIL INDUSTRY IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

In India retail industry is changing dramatically. The transformation in this industry is the best example of India's developing economy. In India, Retail is one important wheel for of its economy and accounts for 14-15% of its GDP , With the sign of development we are scaling up their business and reaping a high profit and funds but we don't have a lot of time to purchase of product from different locations and shops. Today life becomes very busy and many professionals want each and every product under a one shop stop and on the other side of the coin we are seeing that emergence of nuclear families also support the demand of a product and sale. These sorts of reasons provide an opportunity for the ushering organized retail sector that is growing by leaps and bounds in India. In India having a different perspective of consumers towards the product, like some consumers are price sensitive and some are rational thinker the growing middle class is an important factor contributing to the growth of retail in India. By 2030, it is estimated that 91 million households will be 'middle class', up from 21 million today. With all these facts and figures we are trying to figure out some change and growth into Indian retail market, we are seeing some obstacles also in front of business tycoons who are interested to invest into a retail market. Through this paper we want to show a drastic change into a retail sector and how ecommerce websites also helps to grow a retail sector. With the help of secondary research methodology we are also trying to explain the factors behind the growth of Indian retail sector. Today consumer is very important for every organization that's why we are expressing the mood of today's consumers and their inclination towards their brands.

Key Words – *Retail, Market player, Industry, E-commerce, Consumers*

Objective of the study - The objective of the study is to show the status and development of Retail Market in India. As we know India has a large potential in terms of consumers but on the other side India has organized and unorganized retail sector parallel. So we try to show here some relevant issues and information of retail market and also try to understand and show how retail market is performing and developing.

Foreword – India is one of the fastest growing retail markets in the world with 127 million people, now consumption pattern of Indian consumers has changed each and every consumer wants more variety brands in one product. Consumer merely focuses on brand and attractive packaging, so we can say that consumers become more brand conscious and stylish. Indian retail market becomes very attractive because India`s middle class is expected to reach 550 million by 2025-26, more than the combined forecasted population of Britain, Germany, France, Italy and Spain of 330 million, that`s why FDI also become more attractive than earlier. Indian retail industry is going into a high end retail industry phase. Traditional retail is expected to grow at 5% and reach a size of US\$ 650 billion (76%), while organized retail is expected to grow at 25% and reach a size of US\$ 200 billion by 2020. The US-based global management consulting firm, A T Kearney, in its Global Retail Development Index (GRDI) 2011, has ranked India as the fourth most attractive nation for retail investment, among 30 emerging markets. According to Yes Bank – Assocham India`s retail market is likely to touch a whopping Rs. 47 lakh crore by 2016-17, expanding at a compounded annual growth rate of 15 per cent. According to the study, organized retail, which comprised a meager seven per cent of overall retail market in 2011-12 is estimated to grow at a CAGR of 24 per cent and attain 10.2 per cent share of total retail by 2016-17. Amid traditional grocery retailers, *kirana* stores will continue to be the largest contributor to value share by 2016 and are likely to account for 61 per cent share in constant value sales, according to study. Today **Pantaloon Retail Ltd, Lifestyle Retail, Shoppers Stop Ltd, Spencer`s Retail** are growing very well and reaping a high profits.

Research Methodology – This study is based on secondary data and information collected from the variety of sources. This study helps to understand the status of retail market and consumer behavior towards a modern retail market and ecommerce websites.

Literature Review – Various articles and papers have been written by many thinkers and writers on status of Indian retail industry with different focuses some of their key findings have been highlighted down here to have an overall idea . The word consumers. Retailing is beneficial for both retailer and consumer. According to **Philip Kotler** “Retail includes all the activities involved in selling goods or services to the final consumers for personal, non business use. A retailer or retail store was any business enterprise whose sales volume comes primarily from retailing. Any organization selling to final consumers whether it was a manufacturers, wholesalers and retailers- was doing retailing. It would not matter how the goods and services were sold (by person, mail, telephone, vending machine, where they are sold in a store, on the street or in the consumer`s home).”

While barter system is considered to be the oldest form of retail trade. Haats, Madis and Melas have always been a part of Indian market. They will present and trade in various places. The introduction of PDS and evolution of Public Distribution of grains in India in 1939 in Bombay and subsequently extended to other cities and towns. By the year 1946, as many as 771 cities / towns were covered.

The origin of retailing in India can be traced back to the emergence of kirana store and mom and pop shops. These stores facilitate local surrounding people these people used these stores to buy their day to day needs products. Later Government support Khadi and Village Industries commission and set up many rural retail stores and franchise. With 1980 we saw many changes in era of retailing, the first few companies come up with retail chains were in textile sectors for example- Bombay Dyeing, S Kumar`s, Raymond`s etc, later Titan launched retail showroom in organised sector. Retail outlet Food world in FMCG, Planet World and Music World in Music Crossword in Books entered into market before 1995.

History of Retail in India – The origins of retail are old as trade itself. Barter was the oldest form of trade. For centuries, most merchandise was sold in market place or by peddlers. Medieval markets were dependent on local sources for supplies of perishable food because Journey was far too slow to allow for long distance transportation. However, customer did travel considerable distance for specialty items. The peddler, who provided people with the basic goods and necessities that they could not be self sufficient in, followed one of the earliest forms of retail trade. Even in prehistoric time, the peddler traveled long distances to bring products to locations which were in short supply. “They could be termed as early

entrepreneurs who saw the opportunity in serving the needs of the consumers at a profit” Later retailers opened small shops, stocking them with such produce. As towns and cities grew, these retail stores began stocking a mix of convenience merchandise, enabling the formation of high-street bazaars that become the hub retail activity in every city.

In India, the existence of the current *Kirana* format and other shops can be traced to the *Manusmriti* and kautilya`s *Arthshastra* .These text provided guidelines for dealing with customers, after sales service, and quality and price guarantees. Such scholarly works provided the equivalence for exchange is case of barter. They also defined the tax structure for retail and wholesale transactions. He also discussed the manner in which funds and investments could be managed for better results. Indian history and archeology record the existence of markets during the Harappan civilization also. Elaborate descriptions of local and periodic heats have also been found. The new retail formats that are now seen in India have their genesis in Europe.

Factors Behind Growth Of Retail Industry - Many factors are playing a big role to accelerate the growth of retail industry in India are-

- **GROWING NUMBER OF NUCLEAR FAMILIES** - Today many families are splitting up due to some specific reasons but most important is jobs and opportunities ,many jobs and opportunities are available only at specific cities like Bangalore , Pune known for IT jobs . Delhi, Gurgaon and Noida known for Management, Sales and Finance jobs and Bombay know for fashion and Advertising jobs. Merely these locations are not providing these types of jobs but having a more and more opportunities for a job hopper.
- **TRENDS AND FASHION** - In India fashion is also at a high pace and lots of fashionable brands are coming into India and these brands are also evolving a sense of fashion and status into consumers mind. Today`s trend is everyone youngsters want to wear a high end cloths according to our study in India emerging of middle class family support that kind of fashion, trend and status.

- **EMERGING SALARIES AND INCOME** - With the sign of positive business development disposable incomes are also increasing, everyone thinking about to buy a new **Bike, Car, LED, Smartphone** because he/she has lot of disposable income in a very small age.
- **BRAND PSYCHOLOGY** – Today many consumers become Brand conscious , They don't want to purchase any local or small brand they always desire to purchase a high end brand because only of environmental threat ,This type of sensitivity also help to change the portfolio of retail market.
- **SUPERIOR INFRASTRUCTURE** - It is one of the important factors behind for growth of Organised Retail sector. If infrastructure is attractive and impressive then every consumer wants to take a walk into a store.
- **ATTRACTIVE SALES STRATEGIES** – With the emergence of growth of development some sales strategies are also evolving like Discount Offers, Festive Season Sale, One Day Shopping With Heavy Discounts Offer, Seasonal Sales Offer, Discount Offer on Debit and Credit Card, Credit Points on Credit Card Purchasing, Foreign Trips, Free Service for One or Two Year, Membership Discounts Offer, Referral Discounts Offer, and many more. So we can say that these types of sales strategies would be very helpful for many industries and this is also a very important factor.
- **REACHABLE**- Today's market player also try to experiment with the convenient location strategy for their brands, products and services. Through this I am trying to say point of prime location became very important for each and every market player because mostly consumers want to buy a product from convenient store with array of facilities like parking, safety, and not too much rush.
- **ATTRACTIVE E COMMERCE WEBSITES** – Today we are seeing many ecommerce website are coming into a market and they are offering many products at very attractive price and deals .Some websites are playing a very crucial role to change and revive the retail market like **Shop clues, Snapdeal, Flipkart, India**

times and many more brought new ideas of shopping and offering many new brands and quality. E commerce website is one of the most important factors behind to change a landscape of retail market. Online retailer also busy to woe senior citizens like Mumbai based Rahul Upadhyay whose **seniorshelf.com** caters exclusively to senior citizens with mobility aids, toilet safety products and items meant for arthritis patients. E-commerce becomes a very structural and fantastic way to sell their products having no geographic boundaries to access and getting their products accordingly to their operational geographies. On the other side South India based company **oldisgoldstore.com**, it's a online and offline company which sells health care products exclusively for the senior citizens.

- **GLOBALIZATION** – With the emergence of development we also become a globalised so we can think on the basis of global experience and our global experience show an organised retail sector with lot of opportunities, taste and preferences. If we talk about developed countries regarding a retail sector then we can see a well established retail market so I think it is very crucial factor behind development of Indian retail sector.

CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR TOWARDS ORGANISED REATIL INDUSTRY - As we know “According to the investment commission of India, the retail sector is expected to grow almost three times its current levels to \$ 660 billion by 2015”. Today consumer become more comfortable with organised retail sector as we are seeing that more and more investors come up with more innovative ideas of retail business, Many online retail websites are also doing very well like *Snapdeal, Flipkart, Amazon, Junglee , Jabong* etc, and reaping a profits also. Consumer also wants a convenient way of purchasing or we can say that smart purchasing. Over the past 4-5 years, competition from online retailers such as **Flipkart** (in books, music and electronics), **Jabong** (in apparel) has eaten into the revenues of physical retailers. In the present scenario consumer become brand conscious but also care about **quality** and **price**. The arrival of organized retail has also enhanced spending of consumer in general. The reasons indicated for higher spending have been mainly the purchase of larger quantities due to wider range of products, availability of attractive offers like discounts and promotional schemes, and access to better quality products with higher price also.

In Modern business environment consumer becomes very positive and enthusiastic for shopping. Improved supply chain also helps to change the mindset of consumer towards

organised retail sector; it is the very strong point also. Consumers have generally gained with the emergence of organized outlets through the availability of better quality products, lower prices, one-stop shopping, choice of additional brands and products, family shopping, and fresh stocks. Lower income consumers have saved more from purchases at organized outlets. As per a study conducted by the World Gold Council, a first of the kind research is that gold jewellery designing and aesthetics, have actually taken a turn for more designs. The conventional chunky designs don't strike a chord as much, as buyers are more concentrated on jewellery aesthetics with modern design. Study reveals that 75% of the women in India are searching for new design. The Indian market is witnessing an accelerate shift from viewing jewellery as an investment. Isha Datwani, founder of Anmol Jewelers who says, "The biggest change we see is that younger people are buying gold". They know their mind and the influence of elders in the purchase is reducing.

Today many metros become a youngster's hub, actually I am trying to say here some metros become educational hub and some become professional hub and these type of crowd is largely dependent on E-commerce websites and some of them are also a brand conscious.

Conclusion – In India we saw enormous development within 10 yrs. According to the study India's middle class segment contributing their consumption capacity to retail market and become a important ingredient for the growth of retail industry in India. We saw Indian government took many decision for the growth of Indian retail industry, Indeed we can say that Indian retail industry become more competitive within 10 yrs. Today foreign retailers easily and aggressively park their fund with the local partnership and expand their networks and providing a rewarding retail market. India has one of the youngest populations in the world which has a high acceptance of new brands, Shoppers are getting richer faster. In India shoppers are also emerging the wings with digitally and find a new platform for shopping i.e., ecommerce. At last we can say that we are developing with good infrastructure and retail market.

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